

Comparing the Trends of prevalence of Dengue cases before and after the COVID-19 Pandemic in North- East India

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Abstract: Dengue is the most widespread VBD globally, causing cyclical epidemics every 3-5 years. It is affecting the populations of high-risk areas in over 90 countries throughout Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and Central and South America. India is one of the countries that has been reporting dengue outbreaks in recent years. India typically experiences a rise in dengue cases during the monsoon season, which starts around June and continues until November. In 2024, India has not yet entered its typical high transmission period for dengue. However, the country has reported 6,60,487 cases since 2019 which is concentrated in Northern States of India. The paper studies prevalence of dengue cases in North East of India and compare the trends before and after covid- 19 pandemic. As part of result, trends have been observing as 2019 onwards during covid period the cases shows declining trend. On revocation of lock down and opening of market, the cases again start rising. A big jump can be seen after 2022 which again parallels with the previous trend before covid. Major cases area seen in Assam (8208), Nagaland (4943), Manipur (2548), and Mizoram (2060). Plain area shows higher cases than mountain areas. Total cases in Plain areas are 19484 whereas in Mountain areas, it is 8113 only. Deaths are also prevalent more in Plain areas like in Assam (9) and in Manipur (4). Covid- 19 has changed lifestyle of people but at the same time it needs more investigation to study the prevalence of dengue outbreak in North East of India.

IndexTerms - Vector Borne Diseases, Dengue, North East of India, Covid-19, Quarantine.

I. INTRODUCTION

Vector-borne diseases (VBDs) are health related issues caused by mosquitoes and parasites in human populations. VBDs infect more than one billion people annually. Moreover, more than one million people die from these important diseases including Japanese Encephalitis, malaria, dengue, yellow fever, and other VBDs especially in tropical areas. Factors such as unsafe water, sanitation issues, water logging, climate change, global warming, human migration, traveling, the growing trend of international trade, and the human population etc affect the prevalence of vector-borne diseases. (A Global Brief on Vector-Borne Diseases, 2014)

In late 2019, pneumonia cases of unknown cause were reported in the Wuhan (China), and epidemiological surveys showed they were linked to the Wuhan Seafoods and live animals vendors market. In just few months, COVID-19 has grown from a specific area in Wuhan to almost all countries (Chakraborty et al., 2020).

Some efforts have been made to control this unknown and invasive disease, such as lock downs and quarantine period for infected persons, which have affected human contacts and the environment. Therefore, it is expected that reports of VBDs would change during the pandemic. A similar study was performed in Malaysia to assess the impact of COVID-19 lockdown on dengue transmission. The results showed that initially with the lock down days and restrictions in movement of people, it reduced but with the opening of market and life over restrictions, the situation became same (Ong et al., 2021).

In India, the prevalence of VBDs is different. India has wide geographical area with diverse culture and zoo-geographic regions, and climate change impacts simultaneously. According to recent research, transmission of Vector Borne Diseases still prevalent in parts of areas of north India particularly in West Bengal, Odisha, Rajasthan, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. Emergence of new cases have also been reported in areas of Himachal Pradesh and North East of India probably due to climate change (Singh et al., 2020).

Dengue is the most widespread VBD globally, causing cyclical epidemics every 3-5 years.

It is affecting the populations of high-risk areas in over 90 countries throughout Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and Central and South America. As of April 2024, over 7.6 million dengue cases have been reported to WHO, including 3.4 million confirmed cases, over 16,000 severe cases, and over 3,000 deaths. The increase in dengue cases has been particularly pronounced in the Region of the Americas, where the number of cases has already exceeded 7 million by the end of April 2024, surpassing the annual high of 4.6 million cases in 2023 (Dengue - Global Situation, n.d.).

India is one of the countries that has been reporting dengue outbreaks in recent years. India typically experiences a rise in dengue cases during the monsoon season, which starts around June and continues until November. In 2024, India has not yet entered its typical high transmission period for dengue. However, the country has reported 6,60,487 cases since 2019 which is concentrated in Northern States of India (DENGUE/DHF SITUATION IN INDIA:: National Center for Vector Borne Diseases Control (NCVBDC), n.d.).

Recent studies showed that the world has changed since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, and these changes have been accelerated due to increased human interventions. Therefore, we observe drastic changes in the pattern of prevalence of dengue cases, but there is no study has been carried out in this regard. The goal of the research paper is to model and analyse the amount of change in the trends of dengue cases before and after the occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic. This research will help in finding the changing trend of cases and pave the path for unique and pioneering solutions.

Geography of North- East of India

Northeast India comprises eight states: Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Tripura, and Sikkim. This region is uniquely characterized by its diverse geographical features, which include mountains, hills, valleys, and plains. The geography of Northeast India can be divided into three main areas: the Eastern Himalaya and Patkai mountain ranges, the Meghalaya and Karbi plateaus, and the plains of the Brahmaputra river¹. The altitude in this region varies significantly, from almost sea level in the valleys to peaks reaching over 7,000 meters. The region is home to several major rivers, including the Brahmaputra and Barak, with their respective valleys providing fertile plains interspersed among the hilly terrain³. These valleys are crucial for agricultural productivity and support diverse ecosystems characteristic of the subtropical climate of Northeast India. Northeast India experiences a predominantly humid subtropical climate with three distinct seasons: winter, summer, and the monsoon. The monsoon season coincides with summer and is marked by heavy rainfall, making the region one of the wettest areas in India, particularly in places like Cherrapunji, which is known for excessive annual precipitation. (Geographical Location of North-Eastern Region of India. The Collection... | Download Scientific Diagram, n.d.)

Figure 1: North East of India (Road Map (Only NH)),Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region, North East India, n.d.)

Dengue prevalence in North East of India

All referred cases of the Dengue were considered during the five years (before and after the COVID-19 pandemic) to investigate the effect of lockdown on the frequency of the disease.

State	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Arunachal Pradesh	123	1	7	114	130	6
Sikkim	444	11	243	264	311	59
Assam	196	33	103	1826	8208	270
Nagaland	8	1	24	154	4943	4
Manipur	359	37	203	503	2548	64
Meghalaya	82	4	129	26	114	37
Tripura	114	24	349	56	1447	257
Mizoram	42	67	83	1868	2060	234

Table 1: Dengue cases in North East of India (DENGUE/DHF SITUATION IN INDIA :: National Center for Vector Borne Diseases Control (NCVBDC), n.d.)

Results

The annual incidence of Dengue cases are reported in Table 1. Analysis of prevalence of Dengue cases can be seen in Graph 1.

Graph 1: Analysis of Prevalence of Cases of Dengue in North East of India

As can be seen from the analysis of Graph 1, the incidence of dengue cases shows declining trend during covid period since 2019 onwards. On revocation of lock down and opening of market, the cases again starts rising. A big jump can be seen after 2022 which again parallels with the previous trend before covid. Major cases area seen in Assam (8208), Nagaland (4943), Manipur (2548), and Mizoram (2060). Plain area shows higher cases than mountain areas. Total cases in Plain areas are 19484 whereas in Mountain areas, it is 8113 only. Deaths are also prevalent more in Plain areas like in Assam (9) and in Manipur (4).

Discussion

Dengue is transmitted to humans through the bites of mosquitoes. The disease pose a significant global health threat, affecting millions of people annually. The transmission of these diseases is influenced by various factors including unsafe sanitation, water logging, industrial waste, globalization, urbanization, and climate change, making them a growing concern in other part as well. Preventive measures such as sanitation measures, water treatment, safe water,

vector control, and public awareness campaigns are crucial in reducing the burden of dengue and protecting vulnerable populations.

This research paper analyse the change in the epidemiological profile of dengue before and after the COVID-19 outbreak. The present study was designed to evaluate the effects of COVID-19-related quarantine/isolation outcomes on the prevalence of dengue. As shown in Graph 1, the incidence of dengue cases shows declining trend during covid period since 2019 onwards. The reason for the declining trend may be closure of schools, limited population movements, and reduction of physical contact of people, especially among working age group as the high-risk group during lock down. Another reason may be poor collection of data. In covid times, hospitals were engaged in covid- 19 cases and compromised other diseases. Another reason could be people's fear of catching the coronavirus and not going to health centers

Graph 1 shows that on revocation of lock down and opening of market, the cases again starts rising. A big jump can be seen after 2022 where cases again paralleled with the previous trend before covid. Major cases area seen in Assam(8208), Nagaland(4943), Manipur(2548), and Mizoram(2060). This phenomenon can be attributed to some epidemiological and meteorological factors, including being located in the tropical regions as well as unsuitable socioeconomic and health conditions of the inhabitants of these areas.

Graph 1 shows, Plain area have higher cases than mountain areas. Total cases in Plain areas are 19484 whereas in Mountain areas, it is 8113 only. The reason for the non-uniformity may be due to high population in plain areas and economic activities in Plain areas. Plain area mostly practice agriculture where water logging is very common. This gives breeding ground for mosquitoes. High population density and household waste in plain area and development of slum gives breeding ground for mosquitoes and prevalence of dengue outbreak.

In addition, quarantine, movement restrictions, obligatory isolation, and reduction in night movement reduced the contact between mosquitoes and the people. It may be another possible reason for the decrease in malaria cases.

Conclusion

The Covid- 19 pandemic caused tremendous changes in lifestyle of human and the epidemiological pattern of VBDs. Some of the consequences of the COVID-19 can occur in the long term and affect populations after many years. Since the transmission of VBDs are very complex and moreover has several factors for its spread including climate change. Thus, it is important to investigate the data in the post Covid- 19 era.

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